

Visually Transparent and Scalable Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Solar Cells through Spatial Segmentation

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S1 - Aperture area ratio (AAR) and Average Visual Transparency (AVT)

The aperture area ratio (AAR) is a purely geometric parameter that represents the open-area fraction of a spatially-segmented STPV device. For periodic stripes of width W separated by clear gaps S :

$$AAR = \frac{S}{W + S} \times 100$$

Figure 1D shows an %-AAR concept sample with narrow metallic lines $W = 100 \mu\text{m}$; $S = 300 \mu\text{m}$ displayed against a building background, yielding:

$$AAR = \frac{300}{100 + 300} \times 100 = 75\%$$

AAR depends solely on device layout and is independent of wavelength, coatings, colour, or viewing angle. It defines the geometric upper limit of transparency, i.e., the ideal light fraction transmitted if the clear regions were perfectly transparent and the opaque regions fully blocking.

AVT is the perceived transparency of the solar cell, i.e., in this case, including buffer and window layers, which are deposited on top of the complete device and not just on the micro-stripes. It weights transmitted light by human visual sensitivity and a reference illuminant:

$$AVT = \frac{\int_{380}^{780} T(\lambda)V(\lambda)S(\lambda)d\lambda}{\int_{380}^{780} V(\lambda)S(\lambda)d\lambda}$$

Where:

1 $T(\lambda)$: Measured spectral transmittance of the complete device;

2 $V(\lambda)$: CIE photopic response (eye sensitivity under bright light);^[1]

3 $S(\lambda)$: Standard illuminant D65 (standard daylight spectrum);^[2]

4 The AVT of a full module can be expressed as function of the AAR by separating the AVT of the
5 transparent gaps and the AVT of the solar cell covered areas:

6
$$AVT_{module} = AAR \times AVT_{transparent\ gaps} + (1 - AAR) \times AVT_{CIGS/Mo}$$

7 Given that the AVT of our full thickness CIGS/Mo layers is 0:

8
$$AVT_{module} = AAR \times AVT_{transparent\ gaps}$$

9 This means that the light utilization efficiency (LUE) of a module can be expressed as a function of the
10 AAR:

11
$$LUE = PCE_{total\ area} \times AVT_{module} = PCE_{total\ area} \times AAR \times AVT_{transparent\ gaps}$$

12 In the same way, the PCE of the total area is dependent on the AAR, since only the active solar cell
13 area contributes to current generation. Therefore:

14
$$PCE_{total\ area} = PCE_{active\ area} \times (1 - AAR)$$

15
$$LUE = PCE_{active\ area} \times (1 - AAR) \times AAR \times AVT_{transparent\ gaps}$$

16 This gives an inverted parabola relation between the LUE and AAR (Figure S1), with a maximum value
17 of LUE at an AAR of 50%, regardless of the $AVT_{transparent\ gaps}$.

18

19 **Figure S1** – Light Utilization Efficiency / $PCE_{active\ area}$ ratio as a function of Aperture Area Ratio for different AVT values
20 of the transparent gaps (theoretical ideal 100 % AVT and extrapolation for the developed top-down (SLG with 92 % AVT)
21 and bottom-up (SLG/CdS/Window stack with 64 % AVT) devices.

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2 S2 – Calculations of the visual acuity limit of the human eye

3 Visual acuity is the eye's ability to separate two nearby details. It is expressed as the minimum angle
4 of resolution (MAR), the smallest angular separation the eye can reliably tell apart. For a person with
5 normal 20/20 vision, $MAR \approx 1$ arcminute ($1' = 1/60$ of a degree) (ISO 8596:2017(E)).

6

7 In our context, a spatially segmented photovoltaic device composed of many micro-stripes at a distance
8 d , is not visible if two neighbouring micro-stripes form an angle smaller than MAR. Geometrically, for a
9 feature of size s viewed from distance d the viewing angle is $\theta = s/d$ (in radians).

10 Setting $\theta = MAR$, the visibility limit can be calculated:

$$11 \quad MAR = 1 \text{ arcmin} = \frac{1}{60} \frac{\pi}{180} \text{ rad} \approx 2.9089 \times 10^{-4} \text{ rad}$$

$$12 \quad s = d \times MAR$$

13 Thus, at $d = 1 \text{ m}$, features smaller than $\sim 291 \mu\text{m}$ are typically indistinguishable to the observer, and
14 patterns below that scale appear uniform. **Figure 1B** in the main manuscript shows s for typical
15 distances of human activity from a window.

16

17 S3 – Detailed Experimental Procedure

18 Bleach etch route

19 We used a 1 mm thick SLG coated with a 2.2 μm thick photoresist (PR) layer (AZP 4110 Microchem,
20 Ulm, Germany) (**Figure 2A-2**). The PR was patterned into micro lines using a direct-write laser
21 lithography tool (DWL 2000, Heidelberg Instruments, Heidelberg, Germany), with the mask layout
22 designed in AutoCAD (Autodesk, Inc., San Rafael, CA). The exposed PR was developed in AZ400K
23 1:4 dilution (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany), forming the micro-line trenches (Figure 2A-3). All sputtered
24 materials were deposited using a magnetron sputtering system called STAR (SpuTtering for Advanced
25 Research). A 500 nm Mo back-contact bilayer was DC-sputtered from a Mo target (the first 100 nm at
26 47 W and $1.3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mbar}$, followed by 400 nm at 50 W and $6.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mbar}$) into the photoresist trenches.
27 A $\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$ -thick CIGS precursor layer was deposited at room temperature by DC co-sputtering from two
28 CIG targets with Cu–In–Ga compositions of 50–35–15 at% (30 W) and 15–60–25 at% (5 W), at a
29 working pressure of $5.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mbar}$, while selenium was simultaneously evaporated in a pulsed mode
30 (Figure 2A-4). This process yielded an amorphous CIGS precursor film. The excess material on top of
31 the PR was removed by lift-off in an acetone bath, followed by rinsing with isopropanol and deionized
32 water and drying with N_2 . (Figure 2A-5). Next, the sample was dipped in bleach for 60 s to etch the Mo
33 back contact beneath the CIG layer (Figure 2A-6). The CIGS precursor was subsequently crystallised
34 under selenium-containing atmosphere in a horizontal split-tube furnace at 460 °C (TermoLab Fornos

1 Elétricos LDA, Águeda, Portugal), with the samples placed inside a graphite box, under atmospheric
2 pressure and an argon flow of 100 *sccm*, to form the crystalline Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ (CIGS) absorber lines
3 (Figure 2-7). A ~50 *nm* CdS buffer layer was grown by chemical bath deposition (CBD) at 60 °C for 14
4 *minutes* using a precursor solution consisting of cadmium acetate (3.9×10^{-2} M) (Cd source), thiourea
5 (1.3×10^{-1} M) (S source), and of ammonium hydroxide (1.7 M) (complexing agent) (Figure 2A-8). The
6 solar cell stack was completed with a transparent top contact deposited by RF sputtering, consisting of
7 20 *nm* (Zn,Mg)O (50 W, 6.2×10^{-3} *mbar*) and 200 *nm* ZnO:Al (60 W, 5.2×10^{-3} *mbar*), as shown in
8 Figure 2A–8. All sputtering targets (2-inch) were provided by Testbourne Ltd, England UK, and all
9 chemicals were supplied by Sigma Aldrich, Germany.

10 LOR bi-layer route

11 In this approach (**Figure 2B**), all steps were identical to the bleach etch process except that the SLG
12 substrate was coated with a resist bi-layer composed of a 0.8 μm LOR layer (LOR-10B, Kayaku AM,
13 Westborough, United States) at 2500 rpm (**Figure 3B-2**), followed by a 2.2 μm photoresist (PR) layer
14 at 1500 rpm (Figure 3B-3). The resist bi-layer was developed in AZ400K 1:4 dilution for 140 s and the
15 LOR undercut was assessed by optical microscope. The Lift-off was performed in a dedicated remover
16 (Mr-REM 500, Micro Resist Technology, Berlin, Germany) by immersing the samples at 60 °C for 30
17 *minutes* without ultrasonic agitation, followed by 30 *minutes* with ultrasonic treatment (Figure 3B-6).

18 2.2 Top-down fabrication of an STPV mini-module

19 We used 10 × 10 *cm*² complete opaque CIGS solar mini-modules fabricated at the Center for Solar
20 Energy and Hydrogen Research Baden-Württemberg (ZSW) (stack: SLG/Mo/CIGS/CdS/i-
21 ZnO/ZnO:Al), featuring interconnected cells defined by P1, P2, and P3 patterning (as described in [3]),
22 and micro-structured them into an STPV mini-module. The CIGS absorber was deposited with an in-
23 line multi-stage co-evaporation process^[4]. The aperture area efficiencies of the mini-module was 14.0%.
24 The best reference cell on the same carrier exhibits a total area efficiency of 18.4% (without anti-
25 reflective coating), $V_{OC} = 721$ *mV*, $FF = 77.6\%$, and $J_{SC} = 32.8$ *mA/cm*². The fabrication sequence for
26 the STPV mini-module is shown in **Figure 4**. The spatial segmentation process began with
27 photolithography, where the opaque CIGS solar cell (Fig. 4-1) was coated with 2.2 μm thick PR
28 (Figure 4-2). The PR was patterned into micro lines using DWL and developed in AZ400K 1:4 dilution
29 (Figure 4-3). The exposed window layer (and buffer layer below) were etched with a 10% HCl solution,
30 which does not attack the underlying CIGS (Figure 4-4). The CIGS was etched in aqueous bromine
31 solution at a rate of ~153 *nm/min* for a 0.1 *mol/L* concentration (details can be found in [5]) (Figure 4-5).
32 Subsequently, the Mo back-contact was etched with sodium hypochlorite at 40 °C for 30 s (Figure 4-6).
33 Finally, the PR was removed in acetone and the sample rinsed with IPA and DI water (Figure 4-7).

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2 S4 - Area Definitions and Parameter Normalisation

3

4 **Reference Device Area:**

5 The reference measurement was taken from a non-patterned region of the module with 5 series-
6 connected segments. The area was determined from a calibrated optical image using ImageJ, giving
7 6.846 cm^2 ; this value corresponds to both the total and active area of the reference device.

8 **Active Area of the STPV Mini-Module:**

9 The active area was calculated from the designed stripe geometry. Each stripe is 4.7 mm long and 0.4
10 mm wide, and the aperture contains 36 stripes across 5 series-connected segments. This yields an
11 active area of 3.384 cm^2 ($0.47 \text{ cm} \times 0.04 \text{ cm} \times 36 \times 5$).

12 **Total Area of the STPV Mini-Module:**

13 The total area was obtained by adding the transparent regions created by removing material between
14 the stripes and around the aperture. This results in a total area approximately twice the active area.

15

16 **Parameters Calculated Using Active Area vs Total Area:**

17 J_{sc} , R_s , and R_{sh} were calculated using the active area, while PCE was calculated using both the active
18 area and the total area.

19

20 S5 – Possible Defects on the Bleach Fabrication Route

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22

23 **Figure S5** – Cross-sectional SEM micrograph of a defective molybdenum etching with bleach.

24 When comparing the LOR and Bleach route, it became evident that the latter suffered from a bigger
25 variance in the measured optoelectronic properties, possibly justified by the R_{sh} and R_s . From the cross-

1 sectional analysis, we can conclude that the partial etch of the back contact using bleach can lead to
2 possible short-circuit/shunt paths, as evidenced in **Figure S5**, where it's visible how close the window
3 layer, which is deposited everywhere (not only on top of the CIGS), is almost in contact with the
4 molybdenum layer.

5

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